

The karma verbatim quotation

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Last night, our team finished proofreading our article concerning the seemingly overlooked problem of greenhouse gas emissions in military operations and warfare. The article will soon appear in *Environmental Management* [1]. We sincerely hope it will raise a voice to be heard by the world's governments and military powers.

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22 “You once contributed to this *karma* [...]. Now, these
24 vengeful spirits have come to seek justice”.

25 —From “Ghosts”; *The Kingfisher Story Collection*
26 (2022)

28 **The (Largely Unknown) Scale of Military** 29 **Emissions**

30 In the global discourse on climate change, a significant
31 contributor often remains in the shadows: the military-
32 industrial complex. While many efforts are being made to
33 reduce emissions in civilian sectors, the military-industrial

Illustration: The verbatim quotation in the proofing process [1].

Besides, an interesting fact is worth telling. The article starts with a verbatim quotation extracted from [The Kingfisher Story Collection](#) [2]. This short paragraph reminds us, humans, that our own activities, past and present, have triggered many of the grave environmental problems we have been facing. Being too proud of present-day technological advances (especially those mainly increasing fighting prowess) may lead to

not only the so-called “innovation curse” but also future “ghosts” that will likely haunt us for a very long time.

References

[1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2024). The Overlooked Contributors to Climate and Biodiversity Crises: Military Operations and Wars. *Environmental Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-024-01976-4>

[2] Vuong QH. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

